

FAMILY-MARRIAGE RELATIONS, PERIODS OF CRISIS IN THE FAMILY

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ANNOTATION

The article contains information about the family and the relationship between husband and wife in the family. Information about the stages of crisis in the family, the causes of crises is given. The importance of the couple's relationship in the strength of the family is highlighted.

Key words: Family, crisis, marriage, homeostasis, destructive system, constructive system.

Introduction:

Family is a unique social unit, based on the union of husband and wife, kinship relations, unity of domestic life, moral and legal responsibility and upbringing of children by parents established by society, and children's own parents. has certain obligations. The basis of this relationship is the husband-wife relationship. Therefore, in all the developed countries of the world, special attention is paid to studying the characteristics and condition of husband-wife relations, which are the main link of the system of marriage-family relations, in the work related to solving and researching marriage-family problems. Because the correct organization of the relationship between these two members of the family is the basis for good interpersonal relations between other members of the family, for a positive psychological environment to prevail in the family, and for the successful performance of the family's social functions in front of society. and vice versa, deterioration of relations between husband and wife can lead to deterioration of interpersonal relations between other members of the family

The main part

Marriage - in the development of family relations, the mutual relations of husband and wife, the positivity of these relations, mutual understanding of the spouses, emotional aspirations for each other, respect for each other, their satisfaction with their marriage, and the strength of the family, etc. are important psychological factors.

Crisis (Greek krisis - a place where a solution is returned) is a crisis, a breakdown of discipline in a quiet place, a difficult transition period, a sudden strong excitement in something, a strong difficulty in something. A crisis situation is a situation of both emotional and mental stress, a situation that requires a big change from a person and others in a short period of time.

A family crisis is a situation in the family environment, characterized by a disciplinary disruption in the homeostatic process, and disappointment in managing the family. It becomes impossible to solve a new difficult situation with the old used methods. During the family crisis, two potential systems can be developed for the future development of the family:

1. Destructive - leading to disciplinary breakdown in family relations and endangering its existence;
2. It includes the use of potential opportunities in the transition of the constructive (constructive) family to a new level;

The period of family crisis is the most difficult moment that happens between every husband and wife. During this period, it is the main task for the husband and wife not to forget that there will always be resentment, unrest, tears, nervousness and reconciliation with everyone and that this is transitory. It is necessary for both husband and wife to remember that everyone has this period and should not forget its transience, the main task should be to get out of the mill of the crisis safely and whole. But this is not a simple task and not everyone can do it. Whoever succeeds in this will start a long and happy career as in fairy tales

Results and discussion

As a result of the observed experiences and studies, several stages of the family crisis were studied. These are the following:

1. The first crisis - pregnancy and childbirth;
2. The second crisis - the child's speech;
3. The third crisis - when the child begins to communicate with others and establish a relationship, that is, he goes to school and kindergarten.
4. The fourth crisis - the child reaches adolescence;
5. The fifth crisis - when the child grows up and leaves the family;
6. The sixth crisis - the child's marriage (appearance of the bride or groom in the house);
7. The seventh crisis - . the beginning of the period of climax (menstruation) in a woman's life;
8. Eighth crisis - decline of sexual activity in men;

9. The ninth crisis - turning parents into grandparents;

10. The tenth crisis is the death of one of the spouses.

According to statistics, marriage breakdowns occur a lot after 1 year of marriage.

CONCLUSION:

It should be noted that family crises, like the crises of youth, are repeated in everyone. But getting out of this crisis and going through it is manifested in different ways for everyone. The positive impact of the crisis depends on the strength of the couple's relationship and their will power. The family is the foundation of the society, it is in the hands of the members of this family to make it beautiful and meaningful.

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